

EFFECTS OF BATCH AND CONTINUOUS-FLOW MICROWAVE-ASSISTED PROCESS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF CANNABIDIOLIC ACID IN HEMP EXTRACT

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(Received 14th January 2020; accepted 06th April 2020)

ABSTRACT. This research aimed to design, optimize, and compare batch and flow-type microwave-assisted processing using temperature, time, and microwave effects to accelerate the decarboxylation of cannabidiolic acid (CBDA) to cannabidiol (CBD) in hemp extract. The conversion yield of decarboxylation was investigated at different heating temperatures and processing times, and the resulting yields were compared with those obtained using two other methods. The optimum conversion yields of the batch and flow-type microwave-assisted processing of decarboxylation were 90.3% (120 °C for 30 min) and 92.8% (90 °C for 30 min) in hemp extract, respectively. As a result, batch and flow-type microwave-assisted processing are effective and viable methods for the decarboxylation of CBDA to CBD at relatively short residence times and high throughput.

Keywords: *Cannabis sativa L.*, cannabidiol acid, cannabidiol, decarboxylation, microwave

INTRODUCTION

Cannabis (*Cannabis sativa L.*) has been a valuable resource for over 5000 years and has been cultivated specifically for its industrial uses. According to traditional medical records, cannabis-derived cannabinoids have many biological properties, including anticancer [1], anti-inflammatory [2], anxiolytic [3], antipsychotic [4], antiepileptic [5], neuroprotective [6], vasorelaxant [7], antispasmodic [8], antiproliferative [9], antiemetic [10], antibacterial [11], antidiabetic [12], antipsoriatic [13], analgesic [14], bone-stimulant [15], and antimicrobial properties [16]. Over 140 cannabinoids have been isolated and identified in cannabis thus far. Cannabinoids, especially the nonpsychoactive component cannabidiol (CBD), have been widely studied in the pharmaceutical industry. In addition, cannabis extracts containing cannabinoids, including CBD, were classified as novel foods in the European Union (Regulation 2015/2283 on Novel Food). CBD is obtained via the slow decarboxylation of its acidic form, i.e., cannabidiolic acid (CBDA), which is naturally present in plants (Fig. 1). Therefore, an efficient CBDA decarboxylation process has become crucial in the cannabis industry. This decarboxylation process occurs spontaneously in dry conditions and is accelerated by long-term storage, light exposure, and high temperatures. However, despite the importance of decarboxylation in optimizing the transformation yield, few data are

Omega polar C18 column (150 × 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm). For standard aqueous solutions, elution solvents A and B used in the UPLC system were water and acetonitrile, respectively, and each was pumped using two separate pumps. About 3 μL of the standard aqueous solution was injected into the column using a syringe and an elution solvent mixture of A/B (70:30 v/v) at a 0.3 mL/min flow rate. After that, the % volume of the elution solvent B was gradually changed to 100% (20 min), 100% (23 min), and 30% (26 min). Each resultant ingredient isolated from the column was analyzed using UV–Visible (UV–Vis) spectroscopy.

Fig. 2. The calibration curves of CBDA and CBD

Analysis of CBDA and CBD

About 3 μL of the resultant product mixture was injected to separate using UHPLC. The mobile phase in UHPLC contained a binary gradient of solvent A (water) and solvent B (MeCN): 70% B, 10.0 min; 85% B, 11.0 min; 95% B, 15.0 min; and 70% B. The flow rate was established at 0.3 mL/min, and a 220 nm detection wavelength was used. The quantitative analysis was performed according to the calibration curves obtained for CBDA and CBD. Electrospray ionization (ESI)–MS (Shimadzu LCMS-2020 system, Kyoto, Japan) was used for qualitative analysis.

Preparation of Processed Korean Hemp Extract using Batch Microwave Irradiation

The Korean hemp extract was dissolved at a concentration of 100,000 ppm in ethanol, and then the reaction temperature of the reactor was set at 80 °C–130 °C. Further, microwave processing was conducted at a maximum microwave power of 200 W and a frequency of 2450 MHz for 5–40 min.

Preparation of Continuous Microwave Irradiation Equipment

A microwave irradiator manufactured by CEM Company (Matthews, NC, USA) was used as continuous microwave processing equipment. A tube comprising PTFE and PFA was inserted into a 10 mL flow cell accessory reaction chamber to manufacture a continuous reactor. The tube had an outer diameter of 1/16 inch, an inner diameter of 1.0 mm, a length of 127.4 cm, and an inner tube volume of 1.0 mL. After that, the chamber of the continuous reactor was filled with water and acted as a temperature controller by transferring the heat of the water-filled chamber to the tube. One end of a liquid-feeding pump (YMC-KP series) was connected to the inserted tube as an inlet through which the reaction mixture was applied, and the other end was connected to a back pressure regulator of 75 psi (UPCHURCH, P-786) as an outlet through which the reaction mixture was discharged.

Preparation of Processed Korean Hemp Extract Using Continuous Microwave Irradiation

The Korean hemp extract was dissolved at a concentration of 200 ppm in ethanol, and then, the reaction temperature of the continuous reactor was set at 70 °C–100 °C. Continuous microwave processing was conducted at a maximum microwave power of 45 W and a frequency of 2450 MHz for 5–60 min. Each reaction time was controlled by controlling the flow rate of the liquid-feeding pump, and the power was 3–45 W during microwave irradiation. The reaction time according to the flow rate is as follows: 5 min at 0.2 mL/min, 10 min at 0.1 mL/min, 20 min at 0.05 mL/min, 30 min at 0.033 mL/min, 40 min at 0.025 mL/min, and 60 min at 0.017 mL/min. The reaction time represents the time the reactants remain in the tube in the continuous reactor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Batch-Type Microwave-Assisted Processing

Table 1 shows the CBDA and CBD contents expressed in mg/g of the Korean hemp extract after dissolving it in ethanol and irradiating it with batch-type microwave-assisted processing. In the initial Korean hemp extract (Table 1, entry 1), cannabinoids included 68.2 mg of CBDA and 8.9 mg of CBD per 1 g of extract, indicating that the CBD yield and content were 13.0% and 11.5%, respectively. To examine the effect of time and temperature on the CBD yield and content, the experiments were conducted at a microwave processing temperature of 80 °C–120 °C within 30 min. According to microwave irradiation's temperature and treatment time, CBDA in the extract was gradually changed into CBD via a decarboxylation reaction. Consequently, the amounts of CBD in the processed product were increased (Table 1, entries 2–5 and 8). Based on those results, the experiments were conducted at a microwave processing temperature of 120 °C with 10 min intervals (Table 1, entries 6–10). The generated amounts of CBD (62.0 mg per 1 g of extract) reached a maximum after 30 min at 120 °C of microwave irradiation (Table 1, entry 8). Although the % content of CBD was high after 30 min at 120 °C of microwave irradiation, the thermal decomposition of CBDA or CBD occurred after microwave irradiation at 120 °C for 40 and 50 min (Table 1, entries 9 and 10) and high temperatures of over 130 °C (Table 1, entry 11). Therefore, the optimal temperature and treatment time of batch-type microwave irradiation for the decarboxylation of CBDA was 30 min at 120 °C to avoid thermal decomposition.

Table 1. Effect of temperature and treatment time on CBD-generated amounts after batch-type microwave-assisted processing of Korean hemp extract (mg/g)

Entries	Temp. (°C) – Time (min)	CBDA (mg), A	CBD (mg), B	CBD Yield (%) ^a	CBD Content% = {B/(A + B)} × 100
1	–	68.2	8.9	13.0	11.5
2	80–30	58.0	16.7	24.3	22.4
3	90–30	49.1	24.5	35.7	33.3
4	100–30	37.5	31.6	46.0	45.7
5	110–30	34.6	34.1	49.6	49.6
6	120–10	15.3	50.4	73.3	76.6
7	120–20	4.5	61.3	89.2	93.2
8	120–30	2.6	62.0	90.3	96.0
9	120–40	0.6	61.4	89.4	99.0
10	120–50	0.5	60.9	88.6	99.3
11	130–5	1.7	56.8	82.7	96.9

^a CBD yield = B/68.7 mg (theoretical CBD amount at 100% conversion) × 100.

Flow-Type Microwave-Assisted Processing

Subsequently, we examined CBDA decarboxylation in the Korean hemp extract by performing flow-type microwave irradiation. The experiments were conducted at a microwave-assisted processing temperature from 70 °C to 100 °C in 5 °C–10 °C intervals for 5–60 min to examine the effect of treatment time and temperature on the CBD yield and content (Table 2, entries 2–12). The generated amount of CBD reached a maximum after microwave irradiation at 90 °C after 30 min, and CBDA was completely converted to CBD. In addition, the thermal decomposition of cannabinoids occurred after microwave irradiation at a high temperature of 100 °C (Table 2, entries 13–14).

Table 2. Effect of temperature and treatment time on the generated amounts of CBD after the continuous microwave-assisted processing of Korean hemp extract (mg/g)

Entries	Temp. (°C) – Time (min)	CBDA (mg), A	CBD (mg), B	CBD Yield (%) ^a	CBD Content% = {B/(A + B)} × 100
1	-	68.2	8.9	13.0	11.5
2	70–10	55.0	17.6	25.6	24.2
3	70–20	46.9	25.1	36.5	34.9
4	80–10	40.6	31.4	45.7	43.6
5	80–20	25.8	41.2	60.0	61.5
6	80–40	10.3	55.3	80.5	84.3
7	80–60	4.3	58.2	84.7	93.1
8	90–10	17.4	50.0	72.8	74.2
9	90–20	6.3	59.3	86.3	90.3
10	90–30	n.d. ^b	63.7	92.8	>99.5
11	90–40	n.d. ^b	62.1	90.4	>99.5
12	90–60	n.d. ^b	58.9	85.7	>99.5
13	100–5	25.4	36.9	53.7	59.2
14	100–10	n.d. ^b	58.7	85.4	>99.5

^a CBD yield = B/68.7 mg (theoretical CBD amount at 100% conversion) × 100. ^b n.d. = not detected.

CONCLUSION

The decarboxylation of CBDA under continuous-flow microwave-assisted process conditions produced the decarboxylated product CBD in a good yield within a short time compared to batch-type conditions using the Korean hemp extract. However, it is easy to establish a mass production system for industrialization with the batch type, whereas the continuous-flow type requires the development of a system to achieve the same. Nevertheless, the continuous-flow type is economically suitable for industrialization, and it is attractive in continuous manufacturing, which has recently attracted considerable attention.

Acknowledgement. This work was partly supported by intramural grants (2E32611) from the Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KIST), the Ministry of Science and ICT (MSIT, Republic of Korea) (support program: 2021-DD-UP-0379), and the Promotion (NO: P0016080) of Innovative Businesses for Regulation-Free Special Zones and the Technological Innovation R&D Program (NO: P0023712) funded by the Ministry of SMEs and Startups (MSS, Republic of Korea).

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